

DATA ANALYTICS APPROACH TO CYBER CRIME UNDERGROUND ECONOMY USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract—The rapid spread of computer networks has altered perspectives on network security. The ease of access makes computer networks vulnerable to various threats from hackers. There are many threats to networks that can be highly damaging. Researchers have developed Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) capable of identifying attacks in different environments. A variety of methods for detecting misuse and anomalies have been implemented. Many of the suggested technologies complement each other as some approaches are more effective in certain environments than others. This study introduces a novel intrusion detection system for evaluation and categorization. The classification includes the detection principle and operational aspects of the system. In our study, algorithms like Naive Bayes (NB) and Decision Tree (DT) were employed. The accuracy of each algorithm was assessed, revealing that the proposed Decision Tree (DT) outperforms other existing algorithms. Network analysis methods are utilized to clarify the intricate connections among entities operating in the criminal underworld of the internet. By creating and examining charts that depict interactions between users, products, and services, significant players and communities can be pinpointed, allowing for a more profound grasp of the structure and dynamics of the ecosystem. Ultimately, this method of data analysis, supported by machine learning techniques, provides a preemptive plan for countering cybercrime by allowing stakeholders to foresee and lessen emerging threats competently. By means of ongoing enhancement and cooperation, we can collectively strive for a more secure and safer digital space.

Index Terms: Prediction, Accuracy, Malware, Machine Learning NB, DT.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid rise of the digital landscape has heralded a new era of unprecedented connectivity and convenience, transforming how we work, interact, and transact. Nonetheless, this digital revolution has spawned fresh challenges, with cybercrime standing out as a significant issue. Criminal elements have seized the opportunity provided by the internet's anonymity and global reach to carry out various illegal activities, including financial fraud and identity theft, as well as cyber espionage and data breaches. At the core of cybercriminal operations lies the underground economy, a hidden realm where stolen data, hacking tools, and illegal services are bought and sold for profit. Understanding the inner workings of this covert ecosystem is crucial for cybersecurity professionals and law enforcement agencies in their efforts to combat cyber threats

effectively. While traditional cybersecurity methods have their value, they often fall short in addressing the ever-changing nature of cybercrime. Therefore, there is a critical need for innovative approaches that utilize data analytics and machine learning to gain deeper insights into the cybercrime underground economy. In response to this demand, this project suggests an inclusive data analytics approach enhanced by machine learning techniques to dissect and scrutinize the cybercrime underground economy. By tapping into a vast array of data from different sources like dark web forums, marketplaces, and hacker communities, the goal is to unravel the complex network of interactions and transactions that support cybercriminal activities. This summary outlines the main goals, approaches, and contributions of the proposed research endeavour. The text first examines the challenges posed by cybercrime and the pivotal role of the underground economy in enabling illegal activities. It then explains the rationale behind using data analytics and machine learning techniques to tackle this complex issue, highlighting their potential to reveal hidden patterns, spot abnormalities, and predict upcoming threats. Furthermore, an overview of the project's framework is provided, detailing the various phases involved in gathering, processing, and analysing data, as well as the selection and implementation of machine learning algorithms. Emphasis is also placed on the significance of collaboration and information exchange in the fight against cybercrime, stressing the importance of partnerships between academia, industry, and law enforcement.

In conclusion, this summary sets the stage for an innovative research initiative aimed at shedding light on the cybercrime underground economy through the lens of data analytics and machine learning. By leveraging data-driven insights, the objective is to equip stakeholders with the knowledge and tools required to protect the digital realm against evolving cyber threats.

LITERATURE SURVEY

^[1] Over the past few years, ensuring security in wireless sensor networks (WSNs) has become crucial due to the significant sharing of vital information among nodes in these networks. The open deployment of WSNs has led to a multitude of security issues, with attackers targeting different protocol layers to disrupt the system. The standard AODV routing protocol faces security vulnerabilities during the route discovery process, necessitating the secure transmission of data to their destinations. To address these challenges, a trust-based Malware detection system (NL-MDS) for the network layer in WSNs has been proposed to identify Black hole attackers. The trustworthiness of sensor nodes is evaluated

based on deviations in key factors at the network layer caused by Black hole attacks, employing a watchdog technique for continuous monitoring. By considering past and current trust values, the overall trustworthiness of sensor nodes is calculated to efficiently detect malicious nodes involved in Black hole attacks. Performance evaluations conducted in MATLAB R2015a demonstrate that NL-MDS outperforms previous approaches in terms of detection accuracy and false alarm rates.

^[9] With safety critical applications, Internet of Things (IoT), and space-based systems adopting wireless networks based on standardized protocols, the security challenge posed by malicious Malwares has become evident. Malicious Malwares can lead to severe consequences if left undetected, potentially resulting in a complete denial of services, especially critical in applications where any service disruption can be detrimental to safety and privacy. A vulnerability specific to WSNs, known as the matched protocol attack, is identified in this study, highlighting the ineffectiveness of traditional spectral techniques in detecting such attacks. Real-time experiments using a ZigBee cluster head network with ZigBee COTS devices and a spectrum analyser are conducted to analyse the impact of matched protocol interference on a network model. The study explores potential detection techniques based on coarse inter-node distance measurements to detect matched protocol interference and locate the source, aiming to address the identified security risks in WSNs.

^[4] The inherent vulnerability of wireless sensor networks (WSNs) to malicious attacks and data failures poses a challenge, particularly in environmental monitoring applications where false alarms can lead to unreliable outcomes. To ensure a reliable system, the detection of abnormal nodes is critical. A new framework is proposed for detecting abnormal nodes in clustered heterogeneous WSNs, utilizing spatiotemporal (ST) and multivariate-attribute (MVA) sensor correlations. The framework involves analysing collected data by computing cross correlations between sensor streams, aided by identified ST correlations and background knowledge of the monitored environment. By setting thresholds for lag and correlation, abnormal nodes can be detected based on observed MVA correlations, improving the efficiency of capturing correlations and identifying real events within the network.

^[7] Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are particularly susceptible to security threats due to their inherent characteristics, necessitating the development of efficient security protocols that do not overload nodes. A knowledge-based context-aware approach is proposed in this study to address Malwares generated by malicious nodes within WSNs, reducing computational and energy burdens on network nodes. The approach involves using a knowledge base at the base station to categorize events generated by nodes, enabling cluster heads to block repeated malicious activities. Through events logging and analysis, nodes' performance is enhanced by alleviating additional security-related burdens.

^[8] Due to resource limitations and environmental vulnerabilities, body sensor networks (BSNs) frequently encounter faulty sensor data, leading to false alarms and faulty medical diagnoses. A Bayesian network model-based sensor fault detection scheme is proposed in this research to address this issue, utilizing historical training data for establishing conditional probability distributions. By minimizing inaccuracies and tuning fault detection thresholds optimally, the scheme provides a high fault detection accuracy and low false alarm rates, enhancing fault detection efficiency. Utilizing an extensive online dataset, the performance of the proposed fault

detection scheme demonstrates its effectiveness in minimizing false alarms and improving detection accuracy.

^[10] Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) are vulnerable to various denial-of-service (DoS) attacks due to the lack of centralized coordination and inherent security requirements in network protocols. To mitigate selective forwarding attacks like SCAD, a lightweight countermeasure deploying a single checkpoint node is proposed to detect misbehaviour of malicious nodes. Integrated with timeout and hop-by-hop retransmission techniques, the countermeasure aims to recover from packet losses efficiently due to misbehaviour or poor channel quality. Simulation experiments validate the improved detection rates, packet delivery ratios, reduced energy consumption, false detection rates, and successful drop rates achieved by the proposed countermeasure.

^[11] First, the new system model of the novel heterogeneous statistical QoS is developed and analysed utilizing and expanding the theory of effective capacity. Then, our proposed architecture of heterogeneous statistical QoS is applied through wireless coupling channels to effectively implement the following potent 5G-candidate wireless techniques:

1. Device-to-device networks
2. Full-duplex networks
3. Cognitive radio networks

These techniques aim to provide guarantees of heterogeneous statistical delay-bounded QoS. Finally, simulation experiments exhibit the superiority of our proposed schemes and architecture over the traditional statistical delay-bounded QoS provisioning schemes in terms of satisfying heterogeneous delay-bounded QoS requirements while optimizing the overall system throughput across 5G mobile wireless networks.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Naïve Bayes (NB):

In the domain of statistics, the naive Bayes classifiers belong to a group of uncomplicated "probabilistic classifiers" which are founded on the application of Bayes' theorem while assuming strong (naive) independence between the features. Although they are categorized as some of the most straightforward Bayesian network models, when combined with kernel density estimation, they can reach higher levels of accuracy. Naive Bayes classifiers demonstrate high scalability, necessitating only a limited number of parameters that increase proportionally with the quantity of variables in a learning scenario. The training based on maximum likelihood can be undertaken by assessing a closed-form expression, which consumes linear time, rather than resorting to expensive iterative approximation methods as customary for numerous other classifier types. Within the statistical and computer science realms, naive Bayes models can be recognized under various designations, including simple Bayes and independence Bayes. All these labels are linked to the usage of Bayes theorem in the decision-making rule of the classifier, yet it is essential to note that naive Bayes is not automatically a Bayesian technique.

Naive Bayes presents a straightforward approach to crafting classifiers, models that designate class labels to instances of a problem illustrated as vectors of feature values. These class labels are selected from a finite set. There isn't a single unified algorithm for crafting such classifiers, rather a range of algorithms established on a shared principle, all naive Bayes classifiers suppose that the value of one specific feature is separate from the value of any other feature, provided the class variable. In the eyes of a naive Bayes classifier, each feature is deemed to independently influence the likelihood of this fruit being an apple, irrespective of any probable correlations among the colour, roundness, and diameter features. For specific types of probability models, naive Bayes classifiers can be trained proficiently in a supervised learning environment. In various practical applications, parameter estimation for naive Bayes models employs maximum likelihood; essentially, one can operate with the naive Bayes model without espousing Bayesian probability or utilizing any Bayesian methods.

While characterized by their simplistic design and seemingly oversimplified assumptions, naive Bayes classifiers have proven effective across numerous intricate real-world scenarios. In 2004, an examination of the Bayesian classification problem disclosed solid theoretical rationales for the seemingly implausible effectiveness of naive Bayes classifiers. Nonetheless, an extensive comparison with rival classification algorithms in 2006 demonstrated that Bayes classification was surpassed by alternative methods like boosted trees or random forests. One of the benefits of naive Bayes lies in its minimal requirement of training data to deduce the parameters essential for classification.

PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The implementation Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) in serves the purpose of gathering and examining various forms of attacks targeting a computer system or network. This aids in recognizing and pinpointing potential security breaches, encompassing both external intrusions and internal abuses. The current study introduces an integrated model that merges Intrusion Detection (ID) and Intrusion Prevention (IP) systems, incorporating established techniques like intruder Detection (ID). Unlike previous studies that focused solely on either detection or prevention, or utilized different detection methods separately, our approach, termed IDPS, integrates both detection and prevention capabilities. By doing so, our system can effectively halt attacks in progress, a feature lacking in earlier models. This comprehensive system outperforms traditional hybrid setups by not only stopping ongoing attacks but also categorizing them for future reference. When deployed in a Wireless environment, this integrated model significantly decreases the likelihood of potential risks compared to standard or other Intrusion Detection systems. IDSs have a crucial function in protecting computer networks and systems from cyber threats by actively spotting and responding to security incidents. By monitoring network traffic and system activities consistently, IDSs help organizations pinpoint and address security breaches promptly, thus improving their overall cybersecurity readiness and safeguarding sensitive information from unauthorized access or exploitation.

Fig 1: Block Diagram

MODULE DESCRIPTION:

1. Input dataset
2. Analysis of size of data set.
3. Oversampling.
4. Training and Testing.
5. Apply algorithms.
6. Predict results.

1. Input dataset:

Data input comes from online sources to gather a vast dataset for accurate predictions efficiently.

2. Analysis of data set:

The data set's size is analyzed to guide the subsequent data processing steps.

3. Oversampling (SMOTE method):

We have compiled an extensive historical record of malware attacks occurring over an extended period.

4. Training and Testing Subset:

Due to dataset imbalances, classifiers tend to exhibit bias towards dominant classes. The minority class features are often disregarded as noise, necessitating the selection of a smaller dataset sample.

5. Applying algorithm:

The following classification algorithms are employed for testing the sub-sample dataset:

- a. Decision Tree (DT)
- b. Naïve Bayes (NB)

6. Predicting results:

The trained model is put through its paces using the testing subset, with accuracy as the primary metric. An accuracy curve is plotted to visualize the outcomes achieved.

TOOLS USED

OpenCV functions as a repository of programming tasks for real-life computer vision originally crafted by Intel and presently supported by Willogarage. It is freely utilized under the open-source BSD license. With over five hundred operational algorithms, it sees extensive utilization globally, boasting a user base of forty thousand individuals. Its applications span a wide scope from resource communication to thorough auditing and the future realm of robotics. Built primarily in C, it is adaptable to specific platforms like the Digital Signal Processor. Available in various programming languages such as C, Python, Ruby, and Java (utilizing JavaCV).

A. Python

Python has extensive usage across various application domains due to its dynamic and object-oriented nature. It stands out for its support of integration with multiple languages and tools, along with its rich set of standard libraries. Notably, the key features of Python include:

- Syntax that is easy to understand
- Robust capabilities for introspection
- Complete modularity
- Error handling based on exceptions
- High-level dynamic data types
- Support for imperative, object-oriented, and functional programming styles
- Ability to be embedded
- Scalability
- Mature development

With its flexibility, Python allows users to focus on the problem at hand rather than the intricacies of the language, making it an excellent choice for scientific computing.

B. Open CV

Originally created by Intel and now maintained by Willogarage, Open CV is a library of programming functions for real-time computer vision. Available under the open-source BSD license, it offers over 500 optimized algorithms and boasts a user base of 40,000 individuals worldwide. From interactive art to advanced robotics, Open CV finds applications in various fields. Written primarily in C, the library is adaptable to specific platforms like Digital Signal Processor. Additionally, wrappers for languages such as Python, Ruby, and Java have been developed to broaden its reach, with recent releases introducing interfaces for C++. Primarily focusing on real-time image processing, Open CV is cross-platform, supporting Linux, Mac OS, and Windows, positioning itself as the premier open-source computer vision library for developers and researchers alike.

C. Tesseract

Originally developed at HP, Tesseract is a free OCR engine now maintained by Google under the Apache License. Established at the 1995 UNLV Annual Test OCR Accuracy, it can recognize six languages and fully supports UTF8. Users have the option to train Tesseract with their custom fonts and character mapping, enhancing its accuracy and efficiency. Tesseract excels in accurately identifying text from various sources, like scanned papers, pictures, PDFs, and photos taken by cameras. Additionally, Tesseract offers support for more than 100 languages by default, and you can get extra language models and training information for further customization and growth.

OUTPUT MODEL

SIMULATION RESULT

The Accuracy graph is plotted between Naïve Bayes and Decision Tree. Accuracy graph is given in the following figure 2.

Fig 2: Accuracy Analysis

CONCLUSION

Intrusion detection is currently drawing attention from both the research community and commercial companies. Background information on the most up-to-date Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) is provided through a proposed categorization with examples from past and ongoing projects. This categorization emphasizes recent advancements and covers historical and current progress satisfactorily. There isn't a one-size-fits-all solution that can be universally applied against all potential attacks. The selection of the appropriate technique relies on the anomaly types the system is expected to encounter, the data's type and behaviors, the system's operational environment, cost constraints, computational limitations, and the desired security level.

Moreover, incorporating machine learning algorithms like clustering, classification, and anomaly detection improves the system's ability to automatically recognize and classify cyber threats, thereby decreasing the need for manual intervention and response time. Leveraging open-source tools such as OpenCV and Tesseract aids in extracting and processing textual and visual data from various sources like dark web forums, marketplaces, and social media platforms, enriching the dataset for analysis.

FUTURE SCOPE

It is suggested that in future studies, exploration of alternative machine learning algorithms be conducted to determine more effective methods for executing the classification process on the datasets. Further investigations should be carried out on various parameters that could enhance the accuracy of detection. An area for future investigation involves the advancement of real-time monitoring and alerting mechanisms capable of recognizing and responding to cyber threats promptly. Through the integration of streaming data processing frameworks such as Apache Kafka and Apache Flink with machine learning models, organizations can establish dynamic and adaptive cyber threat detection systems that can promptly recognize and mitigate emerging threats as they transpire. In addition, machine learning models have the potential to strengthen fraud detection capabilities by examining transactional data to pinpoint patterns indicative of illicit behaviors like money laundering and identity theft. By utilizing advanced analytics methods and machine learning algorithms, stakeholders can obtain valuable insights into cyber threats, fortify their security defenses, and effectively combat cybercriminal activities in the evolving digital landscape.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. F. Akyildiz et al., "Wireless Sensor Networks: A Survey, "Elsevier Comp. Networks, vol. 3, no. 2, 2019, pp. 393–422
- [2] G.Li, J.He, Y. Fu. "Group-based Malware detection system in wireless sensor networks" Computer Communications, Volume 31, Issue 18 (December 2019)
- [3] Michael Brownfield, "Wireless Sensor Network Denial of Sleep Attack", Proceedings of the 2019 IEEE Workshop on Information Assurance and Security United States Military Academy, West Point, NY.

[4] FarooqAnjum, DhanantSubhadrabandhu, SaswatiSarkar *, Rahul Shetty, "On Optimal Placement of Malware Detection Modules in Sensor Networks", Proceedings of the First International Conference on Broadband Networks (BROADNETS19).

[5] Parveen Sadotra et al, International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing, Vol.5 Issue.9, September- 2019, pg. 23-28

[6] K. Akkayaand M. Younis, —A Survey of Routing Protocols in Wireless Sensor Networks, I in the Elsevier Ad Hoc Network Journal, Vol. 3/3 pp. 325-349, 2019.

[7] A. Abduvaliyev, S. Lee, Y.K Lee, "Energy Efficient Hybrid Malware Detection System for Wireless Sensor Networks", IEEE International Conference on Electronics and Information Engineering, Vol.2, pp. 25-29, August 2019.

[8] Parveen Sadotra and Chandrakant Sharma. A Survey: Intelligent Malware Detection System in Computer Security. International Journal of Computer Applications 151(3):18-22, October 2019.

[9] A. Araujo, J. Blesa, E. Romero, D. Villanueva, "Security in cognitive wireless sensor networks. Challenges and open problems", EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking, February 2019.

[10] A. Becher, Z. Benenson, and M. Dorsey, "Tampering with notes: Real-world physical attacks on wireless sensor networks." in SPC (J. A. Clark, R. F. Paige, F. Polack, and P. J. Brooke, eds.), vol. 3934 of Lecture Notes in Computer Science, pp. 104{118, Springer, 2019.

[11] Heterogeneous statistical QoS provisioning over 5G mobile wireless networks Author: Xi Zhang ;Wenchi Cheng ; Hailin Zhang Published in: IEEE Network (Volume: 28, Issue: 6, Nov.-Dec. 2023)

[12] I. Krontiris and T. Dimitriou, "A practical authentication scheme for in-network programming in wireless sensor networks," in ACM Workshop on Real- World Wireless Sensor Networks, 2019.

[13] M. Ali Aydın *, A. HalimZaim, K. GokhanCeylan "A hybrid Malware detection system design for computer network security" Computers and Electrical Engineering 35 (2019) 517–526.